

OPTIMIZED NUTRIENT-CHLORAMPHENICOL AGAR MEDIUM FOR SELECTIVE ISOLATION OF PSEUDOMONAS FLUORESCENS

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Abstract

Commercially available medium for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas* are relatively expensive. Incorporation of chloramphenicol into nutrient agar has been used in the selective isolation of *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. The aim of this study was to apply optimization in modification of nutrient-chloramphenicol agar medium (NCAM) so as to optimize it for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas* species. Water sample determined to contain fluorescent greenish-pigment producing bacteria (FGPB) was used for the optimization study. Medium component selected for the optimization process were pH, NaCl concentration (NC), and chloramphenicol concentration (CC), with value ranges of 7.0 – 8.2, 0.5 – 1.0 %, and 40 – 60 µg/ml, respectively. Fifteen media variations were derived from combination of these ranges using Box-Behnken design matrix, and were used in culturing the water sample for isolation of FGPB. Relationship between obtained proportions of bacterial populations that are FGPB and chosen media components were calculated using polynomial equation for three factors design. Prediction profiles derived from the equation showed that the highest proportion of bacterial populations that are FGPB was achievable at pH, NC, and CC combination values of 7.0, 0.2 %, and 60 µg/ml, respectively. NCAM with this optimized combination increased the efficiency of selectively isolating FGPB from the water sample from 0.008 to 0.011 %. Physicochemical/biochemical testing showed that the FGPB isolates were *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. It is concluded that NCAM with pH 7.0, NaCl concentration of 0.2 %, and chloramphenicol concentration of 60 µg/ml can be used for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* with optimum efficiency.

Keywords: Box-Behnken design; pH; NaCl; Chloramphenicol; Pseudomon

1. Introduction

Some species of *Pseudomonas* including *P. aeruginosa*, *P. fluorescens*, and *P. putida* are relevant in bioremediation of polluted environments, control of fungal pathogens of plants, and production of certain substances for domestic and industrial application. *P. aeruginosa* is able to produce bio-active substances such as biosurfactants (Mukherjee & Das, 2010; Bustamante et al., 2012), and can degrade various organic substances including hydrocarbons (Ningthoujam & Shovarani, 2008; Singh & Walker, 2006; Ikhimiukor & Nneji, 2013); making it useful in some industries and in bioremediation of polluted environments. *P. fluorescens* is able to degrade various pollutants including herbicides, hydrocarbons, and phenol (Garbiet al., 2006; Mahiuddinet al., 2012; Monekeet al., 2010; Vasudevan et al., 2007), and produce active compounds that portray antagonistic activity against some pathogens of plants

(Anbuselviet al., 2010; Haas et al., 1991). Thus *P. fluorescens* a potential candidate in bioremediation of polluted environment, and in control of pathogens of plants. *P. fluorescens* also produce biosurfactants and antibiotics including Mupirocin, Pyrrolnitrin, and Pyoluteorin (Aboouseoudet al., 2007; Sarniguet et al., 1995; Gao et al., 2014). *P. putida* has the ability to degrade many aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons, toxic pollutants such as styrene, herbicides, toxins, and organic solvents (Marqués & Ramos, 1993; Otenio et al., 2005; Tan et al., 2015), and is therefore also relevant in bioremediation of polluted environments.

An attribute of the principal species of *Pseudomonas*, which include *P. aeruginosa*, *P. fluorescens*, *P. putida*, and *P. syringae*, is the production of diffusible greenish pigments in culture media containing certain substances (Boopathi & Rao, 1999; Daly et al., 1984; Scales et al., 2014; Stanier et al., 1977). The pigments usually fluoresce under ultraviolet (UV) light. Therefore, colonies of the principal species of *Pseudomonas* growing in the midst of colonies of other bacteria on translucent agar plate can be detected in daylight and in the dark under UV light. Production of greenish pigment that fluoresces under UV light can thus be relied upon as a guide in the isolation of any of the principal species of *Pseudomonas*.

Different culture media are available in the market for the isolation of greenish pigment producing *Pseudomonas* spp. They include cetrimide agar, King's B medium, *Pseudomonas* agar P, *Pseudomonas* agar F, asparagine broth enriched with K_2HPO_4 and $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, and *Pseudomonas* CN selective agar (Al-Hina et al., 2010; Laine et al., 2009; Oliveira et al., 2008; Peekate et al., 2018). These media are relatively expensive and not readily available to researchers working in underfunded research institutions.

A substance which appears to instigate pigment production in *Pseudomonas* is the antibiotic chloramphenicol (Peekate & Abu, 2015; Peekate & Abu, 2017a). *P. aeruginosa*, *P. fluorescens*, and some strains of *P. putida* are resistant to some antibiotics including chloramphenicol; and are able to grow in the presence of chloramphenicol, nalidixic acid, and tetracycline (Blanco et al., 2016; Darak & Barde, 2015; Fernández et al., 2012; Livermore, 2002; Morita et al., 2014; Peekate & Abu, 2015; Strateva & Yordanov, 2009). Incorporation of chloramphenicol into nutrient agar, a relatively inexpensive general purpose culture medium, has been used in the selective isolation of *P. fluorescens* (Peekate & Abu, 2017a). There is however a need to elucidate the precise chloramphenicol concentration, and values of other growth medium parameters so as to optimize such medium for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas* species. Therefore, the aim of this research was to apply optimization models in modification of nutrient-chloramphenicol agar medium so as to optimize it for the selective isolation of *Pseudomonas* species.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample collection and analysis

Water sample (500 ml) was collected from a temporary stagnant pool of water near the Microbiology laboratory in the Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Some quantity of the sample was subjected to analysis for bacterial population, while the remaining was stored at 4 °C in a refrigerator for subsequent use in optimization modelling. Bacterial population analyzed for was total heterotrophic bacteria (THB) and fluorescent greenish pigment producing *Pseudomonas* species (FGPs). Determination of THB and FGPs

populations were achieved through 10-fold serial dilution and inoculation on plates of nutrient agar and nutrient agar incorporated with chloramphenicol (50 µg/ml), respectively. Inoculated plates were incubated at ambient temperatures (27 – 32 °C) for 2 days. After incubation, colonies on the nutrient agar plates were counted and used to calculate the THB population. Greenish-pigment producing colonies on the plates of nutrient agar incorporated with chloramphenicol, which fluoresced under UV light in the dark, were suspected as FGPs and their counts used to calculate the FGPs population. UV illumination was provided using a handheld UV torch in a dark room.

2.2 Medium component selected for the optimization process

Medium components chosen for the optimization process include pH and NaCl concentration, in addition to chloramphenicol concentration which served as the pigment-production instigation agent. The value ranges of the medium parameters chosen for the optimization process, based on Box-Behnken design are presented in Table 1(Design adapted from Zhang &Dequan, 2013). Different combinations of the ranges of the medium parameters using the Box-Behnken experimental design matrix are presented in Table 2(Design adapted from Kumar *et al.*, 2015).

Table 1:Value range selection ofmediumparameters for the optimization experiment

Medium parameters	Coded Levels		
	-1	0	+1
pH	7.0	7.6	8.2
NC (%)	0.5	0.75	1.0
CC (µg/ml)	40	50	60

NC: NaCl concentration, CC: chloramphenicol concentration.

Table 2: Combination of ranges of medium parameters for experimentation

CN	pH (X ₁)	NC (X ₂)	CC (X ₃)
- 1	(7.0)	- 1 (0.5)	0 (50)
- 1	(7.0)	+ 1 (1.0)	0 (50)
+ 1	(8.2)	- 1 (0.5)	0 (50)
+ 1	(8.2)	+ 1 (1.0)	0 (50)
- 1	(7.0)	0 (0.75)	- 1 (40)
- 1	(7.0)	0 (0.75)	+ 1 (60)
+ 1	(8.2)	0 (0.75)	- 1 (40)
+ 1	(8.2)	0 (0.75)	+ 1 (60)

2.6 Enumeration of bacterial population using the optimized agar medium

Agar plates of the optimized medium were used in enumeration of bacterial population in the water sample collected from the stagnant pool near the Microbiology laboratory. The result obtained was compared with results obtained using un-optimized medium.

2.7 Identification of fluorescent greenish-pigment-producing bacteria

Some fluorescent greenish-pigment-producing colonies on culture plates of the optimized medium were isolated onto sterile nutrient agar plates, and their stock cultures prepared. The isolates were subjected to Gram staining & microscopic examination, and the following physicochemical/biochemical tests as described in Peekate (2022): catalase test, oxidase test, motility test, citrate utilization test, indole production test, Methyl red tests, Vogues Proskauer test, haemolysis test, casein hydrolysis test, lecithinase production test, lipase production test, and fermentation tests using glucose, lactose, mannitol, xylose, and glycerol.

3. Results

3.1 Bacterial populations in collected water sample

The populations of total heterotrophic bacteria (THB) and suspected fluorescent greenish pigment-producing *Pseudomonas* species (FGPs) in the collected water sample were $2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$ and $1.7 \pm 0.3 \times 10^2$ CFU/ml respectively. This culminates into a proportion of 0.008 % THB that are suspected FGPs.

3.2 Bacterial populations as assessed using media of different combination numbers The bacterial populations in the water sample as assessed using media of the different combination numbers are presented in Table 3. In the Table, it can be observed that the proportions of THB that are suspected to be FGPs in the water sample as assessed using media of the different combination numbers range from 0 – 0.0068 %.

3.3 Polynomial equation generated from the optimization experiment

Fitting of the proportions of THB that were suspected to be FGPs as assessed using media of the different combination numbers and the value ranges of the chosen medium parameters into the regression model (Eq. 3) is presented in Table 4. Resolving the values in Table 4 using the matrix equation $\hat{\beta} = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T Y$ (Draper & Smith, 1998), the coefficients $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_{1,2}, \beta_{1,3}, \beta_{2,3}, \beta_{1,1}, \beta_{2,2},$ and $\beta_{3,3}$ in Eq. 3 for the combinations of value ranges of

the chosen parameters were deduced to be 0.1802, - 0.0425, - 0.0776, 0.0008, 0.0113, - 0.00004, - 0.0002, 0.0023, - 0.0018, and - 0.000004, respectively. Therefore, the polynomial equation from the resolved model is as follows:

$$Y = 0.1802 - 0.0425 X_1 - 0.0776 X_2 + 0.0008 X_3 + 0.0113 X_1 X_2 - 0.00004 X_1 X_3 - 0.0002 X_2 X_3 + 0.0023 X_1^2 - 0.0018 X_2^2 - 0.000004 X_3^2 + \dots \dots \dots \text{(Eq. 4)}$$

Eq. 4 was used in generating prediction profiles which were used in determining the optimized combination of pH, NaCl concentration, and Chloramphenicol concentration for instigating pigment production in FGPs.

3.4 Statistical significance of the generated polynomial equation

A summary of the ANOVA of the polynomial equation derived from the regression model is presented in Table 5. In the Table, it can be seen that calculated F statistics is greater than tabulated F statistics. This indicates that at least one of the coefficients ($\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_{1,2}, \beta_{1,3}, \beta_{2,3}, \beta_{1,1}, \beta_{2,2},$ and $\beta_{3,3}$) Of the derived polynomial equation is significant. This means that a regression model exists between proportion of THB that are FGPs and at least one of pH, NaCl concentration, and chloramphenicol concentration.

Table 3: Bacterial populations as assessed using media of the different combination numbers

CN	THB CFU/ml	CRB CFU/ml	FGB CFU/ml	PTF (%)
1	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$1.75 \pm 0.08 \times 10^3$	$1.50 \pm 0.35 \times 10^2$	0.0068
2	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$8.75 \pm 0.74 \times 10^3$	0	0
3	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$3.35 \pm 0.32 \times 10^3$	0	0
4	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$3.75 \pm 0.25 \times 10^3$	0	0
5	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$2.19 \pm 0.18 \times 10^4$	$5.0 \pm 1.4 \times 10$	0.0023
6	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$2.00 \pm 0.13 \times 10^2$	$2.0 \pm 0.7 \times 10$	0.0009
7	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$1.66 \pm 0.07 \times 10^4$	$5.0 \pm 0.7 \times 10$	0.0023
8	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$6.50 \pm 0.28 \times 10^2$	0	0
9	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$1.23 \pm 0.06 \times 10^4$	0	0
10	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$1.98 \pm 0.08 \times 10^2$	$1.5 \pm 0.4 \times 10$	0.0007
11	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$3.35 \pm 0.32 \times 10^4$	$2.5 \pm 0.4 \times 10$	0.0011
12	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$1.40 \pm 0.03 \times 10^2$	0	0
13	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$4.30 \pm 0.35 \times 10^3$	0	0
14	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$3.45 \pm 0.39 \times 10^3$	$5.0 \pm 0.7 \times 10$	0.0023
15	$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$2.00 \pm 0.35 \times 10^3$	$1.5 \pm 0.4 \times 10$	0.0007

CN: Combination number, THB: Population of total heterotrophic bacteria, CRB: Population of chloramphenicol resistant bacteria, FGB: Population of fluorescent greenish-pigment producing bacteria,

PTF: proportion of THB suspected to be fluorescent greenish-pigment producing *Pseudomonas* species ($\frac{FGB}{THB} \times 100$)

Table 4: Responses from combinations of value ranges of chosen medium parameters

N	.pH	NC	CC							PTF (%)
	X_1	X_2	X_3	$X_1 X_2$	$X_1 X_3$	$X_2 X_3$	X_{12}	X_{22}	X_{32}	Y
1	7	0.5	50	3.5	350	25	49	0.25	2500	0.0068
1	7	1	50	7	350	50	49	1	2500	0
1	8.2	0.5	50	4.1	410	25	67.24	0.25	2500	0
1	8.2	1	50	8.2	410	50	67.24	1	2500	0
1	7	0.75	40	5.25	280	30	49	0.5625	1600	0.0023
1	7	0.75	60	5.25	420	45	49	0.5625	3600	0.0009
1	8.2	0.75	40	6.15	328	30	67.24	0.5625	1600	0.0023
1	8.2	0.75	60	6.15	492	45	67.24	0.5625	3600	0
1	7.6	0.5	40	3.8	304	20	57.76	0.25	1600	0
1	7.6	0.5	60	3.8	456	30	57.76	0.25	3600	0.0007
1	7.6	1	40	7.6	304	40	57.76	1	1600	0.0011
1	7.6	1	60	7.6	456	60	57.76	1	3600	0
1	7.6	0.75	50	5.7	380	37.5	57.76	0.5625	2500	0
1	7.6	0.75	50	5.7	380	37.5	57.76	0.5625	2500	0.0023
1	7.6	0.75	50	5.7	380	37.5	57.76	0.5625	2500	0.0007

[X]: design matrix of the polynomial model, Y: responses of the model, PTF (Y): proportion of THB suspected to be fluorescent greenish-pigment producing *Pseudomonas* species.

Table 5: Summary of the ANOVA of the derived polynomial equation

SOV	DOF	MS	F_c	F_t	α	SOS
		0.0000102	7.29	2.66	0.1	Regression ≡
k	3	0.0000306				
Error ≡ n-(k+1)	11	0.000015	0.0000014			
Total	14					

SOV: Source of variation, DOF: Degree of freedom, SOS: Sum of squares, MS: Mean squares, F_c: calculated F statistic = MS(Regression)/MS(Error), F_t: tabulated F statistic.

3.5 Prediction profiles and optimized combination

The prediction profiles generated from Eq. 4 for chloramphenicol concentrations of 20 – 100 µg/ml and NaCl concentrations of 0.2 – 1.0 %, at pH 7.0, 7.6, and 8.2 is presented in Table 6. From the prediction profiles (Table 6), it can be seen that the highest proportion (0.01 %) of THB that are FGPs can be achievable with the use of modified nutrient agar medium having the following combination: pH – 7.0, NaCl concentration – 0.2 %, chloramphenicol concentration – 60 µg/ml.

Table 6: Prediction profiles for % of THB producing fluorescent greenish pigment from combined concentrations of chloramphenicol (CC) and NaCl

X1 (pH)	X2 (NaCl)	X3 (CC)				
		20	40	60	80	100
7.0	0.2	0.0036	0.0084	<u>0.0100</u>	0.0084	0.0036
	0.4	0.0029	0.0069	0.0077	0.0053	-0.0003
	0.6	0.0021	0.0053	0.0053	0.0021	-0.0044
	0.8	0.0010	0.0034	0.0026	-0.0014	-0.0086
	1.0	-0.0001	0.0015	-0.0001	-0.0049	-0.0129
7.6	0.2	-0.0009	0.0035	<u>0.0046</u>	0.0025	-0.0028
	0.4	-0.0002	0.0033	0.0036	0.0008	-0.0053
	0.6	0.0003	0.0030	0.0025	-0.0012	-0.0080
	0.8	0.0006	0.0026	0.0013	-0.0032	-0.0109
	1.0	0.0008	0.0020	-0.0001	-0.0054	-0.0139
8.2	0.2	-0.0037	0.0002	0.0008	-0.0018	-0.0075
	0.4	-0.0017	0.0014	0.0012	-0.0022	-0.0087
	0.6	0.0002	0.0024	0.0015	-0.0027	-0.0101
	0.8	0.0019	0.0033	0.0016	-0.0034	-0.0116
	1.0	0.0035	<u>0.0041</u>	0.0015	-0.0042	-0.0132

3.6 Bacterial populations in the water sample as assessed using optimized agar medium

Populations of THB in the water sample from the stagnant pool as assessed using nutrient agar, and fluorescent greenish pigment producing bacteria as assessed using un-optimized nutrient-chloramphenicol agar and the optimized nutrient-chloramphenicol agar are presented in Table 7. In the Table, it can be seen that the proportion (0.011 %) of THB that are fluorescent greenish-pigment producing

bacteria as obtained using the optimized medium is greater than the proportion (0.008 %) of THB that are fluorescent greenish-pigment producing bacteria as obtained using the un-optimized medium.

Table 7: Bacterial populations in the water sample as assessed using nutrient agar, unoptimized and optimized nutrient-chloramphenicol agar

THB	FGP(U)	FGP(O)	U.PTF	O.PTF
(CFU/ml)	(CFU/ml)	(CFU/ml)	(%)	(%)
$2.2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^6$	$1.7 \pm 0.3 \times 10^2$	$2.5 \pm 0.3 \times 10^2$	0.008	0.0114

THB: total heterotrophic bacteria, FGP(U): fluorescent greenish-pigment producing colonial count (FGPCC) obtained using un-optimized medium, FGP(O): FGPCC obtained using optimized medium, U.PTF: proportion of THB that are fluorescent greenish-pigment producing bacteria (PTFGB) as obtained using un-optimized medium, O.PTF: PTFGB as obtained using optimized medium.

3.7 Identity of fluorescent greenish-pigment producing bacteria

The isolated fluorescent greenish-pigment-producing bacteria were all Gram negative rods, and reacted alike to the tests used as follows: catalase positive, oxidase positive, positive motility, positive for citrate utilization, negative for indole production, Methyl red negative, Vogues-Proskauer negative, positive for beta-haemolysis, positive for casein hydrolysis, lecithinase positive, lipase positive, acid production from glucose fermentation, negative for lactose fermentation, negative for mannitol fermentation, negative for xylose fermentation, and positive for glycerol fermentation. This results pattern is similar to the physicochemical/biochemical tests results of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* as cited in Peekate (2022). Therefore, all the isolated fluorescent greenish-pigment-producing bacteria are suspected to be *P. fluorescens*.

4. Discussion

Species of *Pseudomonas* are often required by researchers due to their importance in research and application. Media available for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas* are relatively expensive for researchers working in underfunded institutions. The need to modify readily available and relatively inexpensive medium for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas* thus arises. Selective isolation of *Pseudomonas* is made possible by the ability of some of its species to produce fluorescent greenish pigments in the presence of certain substances. Such substances include the antibiotic chloramphenicol (Peekate & Abu, 2015; Peekate & Abu, 2017a). Therefore, modification of nutrient agar, a relatively inexpensive medium, through addition of chloramphenicol presents a cost-effective means for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas*. However, such medium modification needs to be optimized for efficient selective isolation of the target organism, in this case *Pseudomonas*.

In this study, application of optimization models revealed the pH value, NaCl concentration, and chloramphenicol concentration for compounding nutrient-chloramphenicol agar medium for optimum

production of pigment by *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, thereby ensuring efficient selective isolation of the organism. In related studies (Biniarzet *al.*, 2018; Kalaiarasi&Sunitha, 2009; Peekate& Abu, 2017b), application of optimization models have been shown to elucidate medium parameter values, medium components, and culture conditions for efficient production of certain substances including biosurfactants and proteins by *Pseudomonas fluorescens*.

Selective isolation of fluorescent greenish-pigment producing *Pseudomonas* species (FGPs) was achieved in this study, with increase from 0.008 % for the un-optimized medium (nutrient-chloramphenicol agar medium with pH 7.0, 0.5 % NaCl concentration, and 50 µg/ml chloramphenicol concentration) to 0.011 % efficiency for the optimized medium (nutrient-chloramphenicol agar medium with pH 7.0, 0.2 % NaCl concentration, and 60 µg/ml chloramphenicol concentration). In a previous study (Peekate& Abu, 2017a), FGPs was isolated using un-optimized nutrient agar medium incorporated with 50µg/ml chloramphenicol with efficiency of about 0.0002 %. Application of optimization models therefore improved the modification of nutrient-chloramphenicol agar for efficient selective isolation of FGPs.

5. Conclusion

Fluorescent greenish-pigment production by some species of *Pseudomonas* allows for its selective isolation. The production of the pigment can be enhanced in the presence of chloramphenicol. In this study, optimization models were applied in compounding nutrient chloramphenicol agar medium for efficient selective isolation of *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. Medium parameters selected for the optimization process were pH, NaCl concentration, and chloramphenicol concentration. Values of these parameters that allowed for efficient selective isolation of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* as determined through optimization models were as follows: pH – 7.0, NaCl concentration – 0.2 %, chloramphenicol concentration – 60 µg/ml. Therefore, nutrient-chloramphenicol agar medium with pH 7.0, NaCl concentration of 0.2 %, and chloramphenicol concentration of 60 µg/ml can be used for selective isolation of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* with optimum efficiency.

Disclosure of conflict of interest There are no conflicts of interest.

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